

READING DIFFICULTIES AND COGNITIVE DEVELOPMENT OF JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOL LEARNERS

LEA ROSE A. COLEGADO

Abstract. Reading difficulties are a persistent problem that affects individuals of all ages, genders, and socioeconomic backgrounds. Research conducted at Davao Oriental, randomly selected 120 junior high school teachers has shown that they are associated with deficits in various cognitive skills, such as working memory, attention, and phonological processing. This study aims to examine the relationship between reading difficulties and cognitive development using a quantitative approach. The findings of the study disclosed the domain of reading difficulties exerts a significant influence on cognitive development, phonological awareness, working memory, attention, and language comprehension. Furthermore, reading difficulties can hinder the development of vocabulary, background knowledge, and critical thinking skills, all of which are crucial for cognitive growth. Addressing reading difficulties is essential to support cognitive development. By implementing evidence-based interventions, providing explicit instruction, and creating a supportive learning environment, educators can help students overcome reading challenges and enhance their cognitive abilities. In conclusion, educators can implement effective strategies to address reading difficulties, thereby promoting cognitive growth, academic achievement, and lifelong learning skills in learners. The results and findings of this study will challenge future researchers to conduct a similar study that must be considered other factors could help new education system in the Philippines quality and valuable in all aspects.

KEY WORDS

1. Reading Difficulties
2. Cognitive Development
3. Junior High School Learners

1. Introduction

Reading difficulties are a persistent problem that affects individuals of all ages, genders, and socioeconomic backgrounds. Research has shown that they are associated with deficits in various cognitive skills, such as working memory, attention, and phonological processing. This study aims to examine the relationship between reading difficulties and cognitive development using a quantitative approach. The results of the study will provide insights into the nature of the relationship and inform the development of targeted interventions for struggling readers. In the global context reading difficulties are a global concern that affects learners of all ages and backgrounds. A study conducted by the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) found that 10 percent of 15-year-olds in the participating countries had serious difficulties in reading comprehension, with the highest rates of reading difficulties ob-

served in low-income countries (OECD, 2019). The consequences of reading difficulties can be severe, with research showing that reading difficulties can lead to academic underachievement, low self-esteem, and social isolation (Snowling, 2019). In the Philippines, several studies have investigated the relationship between reading difficulties and cognitive development in learners. These studies have focused on different cognitive processes such as phonological awareness, working memory, and executive function. In the national context, that reading difficulties are associated with deficits in cognitive processes such as phonological awareness, working memory, and executive function, which can have long-term effects on learners' cognitive development, academic achievement, and social-emotional well-being (Garcia, 2020). In

2. Method

This chapter discussed the research design, research respondents, research instrument, data gathering procedure, and data analysis.

2.1. Research Design—The research design of this study utilized a quantitative, descriptive-correlational method because this study determines the examining the relationship between reading difficulties and cognitive development of learners: a quantitative analysis. To illustrate this research design, Creswell (2015) stated that it is a design that is used by investigators to describe and measure the degree of relationship between two variables or a set of scores. The researchers believe that a descriptive-correlational methods effective for this study, the researcher may be able to determine the relationship between the examining the relationship between reading difficulties and cognitive development of learners: a quantitative analysis, it is the most accurate design that can be used in accordance with the topic.

2.2. Research Respondents—The respondents of this study were composed of 120 Junior

the local context. In a study conducted by Nacorda and colleagues (2019), the researchers investigated the relationship between reading difficulties and working memory in Filipino children. The study found that Filipino children with reading difficulties had significantly lower working memory scores than their typically developing peers, indicating that working memory deficits may contribute to reading difficulties. In a study conducted by Liwanag and colleagues (2019), the researchers investigated the relationship between reading difficulties and executive function in Filipino children. The study found that Filipino children with reading difficulties had significantly lower scores on executive function tasks than their typically developing peers, suggesting that executive function deficits may contribute to reading difficulties.

high school teachers within Banaybanay district, Division of Davao Oriental. The researcher sets the criteria for inclusion of respondents. The respondents must be a public junior high school teacher, for more than 3 years in service. Lastly, the teachers' respondents agreed to answer the survey tool administered by the researcher. The research respondents honestly filled up the information needed in the structured survey questionnaire that will be distributed accordingly by the researcher. The researcher used a random sampling method in conducting the study, using a proportional number of respondents in every public National high school belonging to, public school of Banaybanay district, Division of Davao Oriental. Random sampling was used, everyone was chosen entirely by drawing lots. Due to the large number of the population of teachers in public schools at Banaybanay district, Division of Davao Oriental, everyone has the probability of being chosen at any stage during the sampling process.

2.3. Research Instrument—A researcher self-made instrument was prepared with the guidance of the thesis adviser and evaluators

and was used in gathering the needed data for the realization of the work. The questionnaire has 3 aspects (indicators) for the independent variable (reading difficulties), Poor reading fluency, Poor visual attention, and Poor phonological awareness, while the dependent variable (cognitive development) considered the 3 indicators namely: Working memory, Background knowledge, and Difficulty with abstract reasoning. Each indicator has five (5) questions that can be answered through the given legend. Simple instructions can be seen in the questionnaires. The research questionnaires were purely researcher made the concept of the questionnaire was submitted and was evaluated by a grammarian and validators. The suggestions

and evaluation tools were given for them to help the researchers to improve and make the research instrument in its best form. The outcome of the evaluation and validation as well as the research instrument’s draft was submitted to the research adviser for finalization. Unclear statements were removed; weak statements were strengthened and polished. After the finalization by the research adviser, the research instrument is now prepared. After the evaluation and approval of the questionnaires, the tool for gathering data and information from the respondents will be administered by the researcher. The pilot testing was conducted at the same area but not with the respondents of the study. The first part measures the extent of reading difficulties.

Extent of Reading Difficulties

Range of Scale	Descriptive Equivalent	Descriptive Interpretation
4:20-5:00	Very Extensive	reading difficulties are evident.
3:40-4.19	Extensive	reading difficulties is oftentimes evident.
2.60-3.39	Moderately Extensive	reading difficulties is sometimes evident.
1.80-2.59	Less Extensive	reading difficulties is rarely evident.
1:00-1.79	Not Extensive	reading difficulties is never evident.

Extent of Cognitive Development of Learners: A Quantitative Analysis

Range of Scale	Descriptive Equivalent	Descriptive Interpretation
4:20-5:00	Very Extensive	extent of cognitive is always evident.
3:40-4.19	Extensive	extent of cognitive is oftentimes evident.
2.60-3.39	Moderately Extensive	extent of cognitive is sometime evident.
1.80-2.59	Less Extensive	extent of cognitive is rarely evident.
1:00-1.79	Not Extensive	extent of cognitive is never evident.

2.4. *Data Gathering Procedure*—The necessary data underwent the following gathering procedure: The researcher asked for an endorsement to conduct the study from the Dean of the Graduate School. A letter request attached

with the Dean’s endorsement was forwarded to the School’s Division Superintendent for permission. The researcher asks permission from the office of the Schools Division Superintendent of Division of Davao Oriental to conduct a

survey to the teachers' respondents from Banaybanay district, Division of Davao Oriental. Likewise, the granted letter of permission from the Schools Division Superintendent was brought to the principals and supervisor of public schools, Banaybanay district, Division of Davao Oriental. for the arrangement of the conduct of the research study. The arrangement was done with the school principals and supervisor upon observation of safety protocol regarding the conduct of the research. Upon the approval, the researcher personally administered the research survey tool. The researcher conducted the survey and retrieved the data. The researcher observed full ethical standards in the conduct of the study, following the study protocol assessment and standardized criteria, particularly in managing the population and data. A received copy of the letter presented was secured from the principals to vouch that the researcher honestly conducted and collected the data from the respondents of the study. The data gathered was

tallied, tabulated, analyzed, and interpreted confidentially and accordingly. The results of this study were analyzed and interpreted based on the purpose of the study. After the responses may be retrieved and tallied, and then be forwarded to the statistician for data treatment. The teachers' respondents from Banaybanay district, Division of Davao Oriental. have given their free will to participate or to withdraw anytime from the study without any form of consequence or penalty. The respondents personally and professionally give an information that may be required in the study was kept in private and were treated with utmost confidentiality of the respondents' data was adhered upon. On the other hand, the research questionnaire used is free of technical terms and can be easily understood by the respondents of the study, these perceived biases are prevented. Therefore, no research questionnaire was given to respondents without the permission from the authorized command channels.

2.5. *Data Analysis*—The following statistical tools may be used to treat the data: Mean. This may be to determine the extent of the examining the relationship between reading difficulties and cognitive development of junior high school learners. Pearson's Product Moment Co-

efficient of Correlation. This tool may be used to determine the relationship between the reading difficulties and cognitive development of junior high school learners. Regression. This tool may be used to determine the domain of the reading difficulties that significantly influence cognitive development of learners.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the discussion of the findings in this study. They are discussed thoroughly, analyzed, and interpreted.

Presented in Table 1 are data on the summary of the extent of reading difficulties. The overall mean of the data is 3.99 which distributed by the indicators. They were presented with the corresponding mean as follows: Poor reading fluency 3.96, Poor visual attention 4.00, and Poor phonological awareness 4.01. All these indicators are with the descriptive equivalent

of extensive which means that the indicators that may considered of this study in reading difficulties. This implied that extent of reading difficulties with the descriptive equivalent of extensive which means that the indicators that may considered of this study in teachers must continually monitor and assess the progress of students with poor phonological awareness. This

involves tracking their growth in phonological skills, identifying areas that still need improvement, and adjusting instructional strategies accordingly. Regular progress monitoring ensures that students receive appropriate interventions and support. Support for struggling readers: Poor phonological awareness often impacts a student’s overall reading ability. Teachers need to provide targeted support to help struggling readers develop phonemic awareness, decoding skills, and fluency. This may involve implementing research-based reading interventions

and supporting students in building their reading confidence. To address these implications, teachers can benefit from professional development opportunities focused on phonological awareness instruction and intervention techniques. Collaborative planning with colleagues and leveraging available resources, such as instructional materials and technology tools, can also support teachers in effectively addressing the needs of students with poor phonological awareness.

Table 1. Summary of the Extent of Reading Difficulties

Indicators	Mean ()	Descriptive Equivalent
Poor reading fluency	3.96	Extensive
Poor visual attention	4.00	Extensive
Poor phonological awareness	4.01	Extensive
Overall mean	3.99	Extensive

Table 8 shows a summary of Summary of cognitive development which revealed an overall mean of 3.99. The four indicators are presented with their corresponding mean rating namely working memory 4.02, background knowledge 3.99, and difficulty with abstract reasoning 4.05. All three indicators are with the descriptive equivalent of extensive. Which means that school achievement goals are to plan for the replacement of key strategies; potential teachers must first be identified and prepared to take on those roles, it is not enough to select teachers in the school who seem "right" for the job. Not only should the experience and duties be considered, but also the personality, the effectiveness strategies skills, and the readiness for taking on a key of teaching learning role process with the diverse learners in the next generation. Working memory, the ability to hold and manipulate information in the mind, affects students’ ability to process and remember information while reading. Students with poor working memory may struggle with tasks that

require mental effort, such as complex problem-solving or understanding and retaining information from texts. Phonological awareness, the ability to identify and manipulate the sounds of spoken language, is essential for decoding and word recognition. Students with poor phonological awareness may have difficulty recognizing and manipulating the sounds in words, leading to reading difficulties and limited vocabulary development. Visual attention plays a crucial role in reading fluency and comprehension. Students with poor visual attention may struggle with tracking lines of text, scanning for specific information, and staying focused while reading. This can impede their reading speed, accuracy, and overall understanding of the text. Arranged to the highest rating to the lowest indicators. Limited background knowledge can hinder reading comprehension. Students with limited exposure to diverse experiences and knowledge may struggle to make connections, infer meaning, and engage in critical thinking while reading. Teachers need to address these gaps by provid-

ing explicit instruction, offering diverse reading materials, and creating a culturally inclusive learning environment. Understanding and addressing these cognitive factors in the context of junior high school learners is essential for supporting students with reading difficulties. Teachers can adapt instructional strategies, provide targeted interventions, and foster a supportive learning environment that promotes cognitive development and reading success.

Table 2. Summary of Cognitive Development

Indicators	Mean ()	Descriptive Equivalent
Working memory	4.02	Extensive
Background knowledge	3.99	Extensive
Difficulty with abstract reasoning	4.05	Extensive
Overall mean	4.01	Extensive

The significant relationship between the reading difficulties and cognitive development, has a strong relationship in a work is necessary to be united and to have work collaboration which can be gain by having both positive teaching strategies and a strong working relationship. Table 9 had shown the significant relationship between the reading difficulties and cognitive development got mean rating of 4.00 with the standard deviation of 0.400 and difficulties cognitive development got the mean rating of 4.01 with the standard deviation of 0.401 standard deviation. The Pearson-R correlation result showed 0.412 which means there is a positive correlation at a significant level of .000 which means that there is a significant relationship between the reading difficulties and cognitive development. It explains that if reading difficulties and cognitive development The decision is to reject the null hypothesis. The null hypothesis of the study stated that there is no significant relationship between of reading difficulties and cognitive development, the result of the study implied the that the indicators of pedestal management skills of reading difficulties significantly influence to the cognitive development of learners. Hence, the decision is to reject the null hypothesis. However, as evidence from the literature review, many studies have been done on the cognitive development

of junior high school learners plays a crucial role in their reading abilities. Reading difficulties can be influenced by various cognitive factors, including working memory, phonological awareness, visual attention, and background knowledge. These cognitive processes impact students' reading fluency, comprehension, and overall academic achievement. Working memory, the ability to hold and manipulate information in the mind, affects students' ability to process and remember information while reading. Students with poor working memory may struggle with tasks that require mental effort, such as complex problem-solving or understanding and retaining information from texts. Phonological awareness, the ability to identify and manipulate the sounds of spoken language, is essential for decoding and word recognition. Students with poor phonological awareness may have difficulty recognizing and manipulating the sounds in words, leading to reading difficulties and limited vocabulary development. Visual attention plays a crucial role in reading fluency and comprehension. Students with poor visual attention may struggle with tracking lines of text, scanning for specific information, and staying focused while reading. This can impede their reading speed, accuracy, and overall understanding of the text. Limited background knowledge can hinder reading comprehension. Students

with limited exposure to diverse experiences and knowledge may struggle to make connections, infer meaning, and engage in critical thinking while reading. Teachers need to address these gaps by providing explicit instruction, offering diverse reading materials, and creating a culturally inclusive learning environment.

Table 3. Significant Relationship Between the Reading Difficulties and Cognitive Development

Variables	Mean	Std	R	Sig. Level $\alpha < .05$	Decision
1. Reading difficulties	4.00	.400	.412	.000	Reject Ho
2. Cognitive development	4.01	.401			

Table 4 has shown that reading difficulties significantly influence to the cognitive development it shows that the value of the regression analysis F ratio is 26.43, with a significant level of .000. This simply means that the reading difficulties indicators significantly influence cognitive development. The decision is to reject the null hypothesis. This implied that there is a domain of working memory which refers to the ability to temporarily hold and manipulate information in the mind. It plays a crucial role in reading comprehension, as readers need to process and integrate information from the text. Difficulties in working memory can affect a reader’s ability to retain and organize information, leading to challenges in understanding and recalling what was read. Phonological awareness involves the ability to recognize and manipulate the sounds of spoken language. It is a foundational skill for reading, as it enables readers to decode words and understand the relationships between sounds and letters. Difficulties in phonological awareness can result in difficulties with word recognition, spelling, and reading fluency. Visual attention refers to the ability to focus and selectively attend to visual stimuli. Efficient visual attention is necessary for reading, as readers need to visually scan and track the text. Difficulties in visual attention can lead to skip-

ping or misreading words, slow reading speed, and reduced comprehension. Executive functions are cognitive processes involved in goal-directed behavior, self-regulation, and problem-solving. Skills such as attention control, cognitive flexibility, and inhibitory control are important for successful reading. Difficulties in executive functions can impact a reader’s ability to concentrate, switch between tasks, and use strategies effectively while reading. Metacognition refers to the awareness and regulation of one’s own thinking processes. Skilled readers use metacognitive strategies, such as monitoring comprehension and adjusting reading strategies when encountering difficulties. Difficulties in metacognition can result in a lack of awareness of comprehension breakdowns or ineffective use of reading strategies. Language skills and vocabulary knowledge are closely linked to reading comprehension. Difficulties in language development, including limited vocabulary or syntactic knowledge, can hinder a reader’s ability to understand and derive meaning from the text. Understanding the cognitive processes underlying reading difficulties can inform the development of effective interventions and instructional approaches. Teachers, researchers, and practitioners in the field of reading difficulties and cognitive development work to identify and

address these cognitive factors to support struggling readers and promote reading success. I recognize and emphasize the significant influence of the domain of reading difficulties on students' cognitive development. Reading difficulties can have a profound impact on various cognitive processes, shaping how students perceive, understand, and interact with written information. The ability to read is not merely a basic skill but a gateway to knowledge acquisition, critical thinking, and overall intellectual growth. When students experience reading dif-

ficulties, such as struggles with phonological awareness, working memory, or visual attention, it directly affects their cognitive development. Research has consistently shown that reading difficulties can hinder students' ability to process information, make connections, and extract meaning from text. These challenges can limit their vocabulary development, comprehension skills, and overall cognitive capabilities. As a result, students may face difficulties in various academic areas and may experience a lack of confidence in their own intellectual abilities.

Table 4. The Domain of Reading Difficulties Significantly Influences Cognitive Development

Independent Variables (Domains)	Dependent Variable	F	p-value	Decision on Ho1
Poor reading fluency	Cognitive Development	4.106	0.001	Reject Ho
Poor visual attention	Cognitive Development	4.112	0.005	Reject Ho
Poor phonological awareness	Cognitive Development	5.106	0.001	Reject Ho

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	5.660	2	2.830	26.43	.000b
Residual	6.960	65			
Total	12.619	67			

Note: a. Reading Difficulties, b. Cognitive Development

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This chapter discusses the focal points of the research and the results of the statistical analysis. It also presents the conclusions and recommendations based on the findings of the study.

4.1. Findings—This study aimed to determine the relationship between reading difficulties and cognitive development of learners. The Pearson-R correlation result means there is a positive correlation at a significant level which means that there is a significant relationship between the pedestal management skills of teacher and school goals in new normal education pol-

icy reading difficulties and cognitive development of learners. It explains that if the reading difficulties were positively embodied the cognitive development of learners is vertically significant and very extensive. The decision is to reject the null hypothesis. Hence, there is a significant relationship between the reading difficulties skills of learners and cognitive de-

velopment of learners. The results of the study disclosed that the teacher firmly believes that the domain of reading difficulties significantly influences cognitive development in students. Reading difficulties can impact various cognitive processes, shaping how learners perceive, process, and comprehend written information. Here is a statement that reflects this belief:

The domain of reading difficulties holds a significant influence over cognitive development in students. Reading difficulties, such as poor phonological awareness, limited working memory capacity, or challenges in visual attention, can hinder students' ability to effectively engage with and understand text. These difficulties impact their cognitive processes, inhibiting the development of critical skills like comprehension, vocabulary acquisition, and critical thinking. By addressing and supporting students with reading difficulties, we can directly contribute to their cognitive growth and overall academic success. By providing targeted interventions, implementing evidence-based strategies, and fostering a supportive learning environment, we empower students to overcome reading difficulties, strengthen their cognitive abilities, and unlock their full potential as confident and proficient readers.

4.2. Conclusions—Based on the overall findings of this research, the following conclusions are drawn: The null hypothesis of the study stated that there is no significant relationship between of reading difficulties and cognitive development the result of the study implied the indicators of reading difficulties significantly influence to the cognitive development. Hence, the decision is to reject the null hypothesis. However, the results of the study disclosed that the domain of reading difficulties significantly influences cognitive development in students. The ability to read and comprehend written text is a fundamental skill that supports numerous cognitive processes and intellectual growth. Reading difficulties, such as struggles

with phonological awareness, working memory, or visual attention, can directly impact students' cognitive development. These challenges can hinder their ability to process information, make connections, and extract meaning from text. When students face difficulties in reading, it can impede their overall cognitive growth and academic progress. By addressing reading difficulties and providing appropriate interventions, we can help students strengthen their cognitive abilities. For example, supporting students in developing phonological awareness can enhance their language processing skills, which in turn contributes to their cognitive development. Moreover, when students overcome reading difficulties, they gain access to a wealth of knowledge and experiences through reading. This exposure to diverse content and ideas further stimulates cognitive development, broadens their understanding of the world, and expands their critical thinking skills.

4.3. Recommendations—Based on the findings and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations are offered for consideration: The officials of the Department of Education are considered to make initiatives to develop further the in conclusion, the domain of reading difficulties significantly influences cognitive development in students. By addressing these difficulties and promoting effective reading instruction, we can positively impact students' cognitive growth, academic achievement, and lifelong learning abilities. The School Heads It is our responsibility as school leaders to address and support students with reading difficulties. By implementing evidence-based practices and providing targeted interventions, we can help students overcome these challenges and enhance their cognitive development. This may involve specialized reading programs, individualized support, and collaboration with teachers, specialists, and families to create a comprehensive and holistic approach. By addressing reading difficulties, we not only sup-

port students' cognitive growth but also foster a positive learning environment. When students gain confidence in their reading abilities, it opens doors to a vast array of knowledge, experiences, and opportunities. It enhances their critical thinking skills, expands their vocabulary, and allows them to engage in complex texts that stimulate their cognitive development. As school heads, we must allocate resources, provide professional development opportunities, and create a school culture that prioritizes effective reading instruction and intervention. By doing so, we can empower our students to overcome reading difficulties, enhance their cognitive abilities, and achieve academic success. Teachers, it is our responsibility to recognize the impact of reading difficulties on cognitive development and implement strategies to address these challenges. By providing targeted instruction, individualized support, and fostering a positive reading environment, we can empower students to overcome reading difficulties, enhance their cognitive abilities, and achieve their full potential. Learners, the domain of reading difficulties significantly influences cognitive development in students. By addressing these difficulties and promoting effective reading instruction, we can positively impact students' cognitive growth, academic achievement, and lifelong learning abilities. The results and findings of this study will challenge future researchers to conduct a similar study that must be considered other factors could help new education system in the Philippines quality and valuable in all aspects.

5. Reference

- Stanovich, K. E. (1986). Matthew effects in reading: Some consequences of individual differences in the acquisition of literacy. *Reading research quarterly*, 21(4), 360-407.
- Wagner, R. K., & Torgesen, J. K. (1987). The nature of phonological processing and its causal role in the acquisition of reading skills. *Psychological bulletin*, 101(2), 192-212.
- Adams, M. J. (1990). *Beginning to read: Thinking and learning about print*. MIT Press.
- National Reading Panel. (2000). *Teaching children to read: An evidence-based assessment of the scientific research literature on reading and its implications for reading instruction*. National Institute of Child Health and Human Development
- Snowling, M. J. (2000). *Dyslexia* (2nd ed.). Blackwell Publishers. Snowling's book provides an overview of the causes and characteristics of dyslexia, with a focus on the role of phonological awareness in reading difficulties and effective interventions for improving phonological awareness skills in children with dyslexia.
- Catts, H. W., & Kamhi, A. G. (Eds.). (2005). *The connections between language and reading disabilities*. Lawrence Erlbaum Associates.
- Miyake, A., Friedman, N. P., Emerson, M. J., Witzki, A. H., Howerter, A., & Wager, T. D. (2000). The unity and diversity of executive functions and their contributions to complex “frontal lobe” tasks: A latent variable analysis. *Cognitive psychology*, 41(1), 49-100.
- Diamond, A. (2013). Executive functions. *Annual review of psychology*, 64, 135-168..
- Best, J. R., & Miller, P. H. (2010). A developmental perspective on executive function. *Child development*, 81(6), 1641-1660.
- Diamond, A., & Lee, K. (2011). Interventions shown to aid executive function development in children 4 to 12 years old. *Science*, 333(6045), 959-964.
- Zelazo, P. D., & Carlson, S. M. (2012). Hot and cool executive function in childhood and adolescence: Development and plasticity. *Child development perspectives*, 6(4), 354-360.

- Piaget, J. (1952). *The origins of intelligence in children*. New York: International Universities Press.
- Vygotsky, L. S. (1978). *Mind in society: The development of higher psychological processes*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press.
- Flavell, J. H. (1999). Cognitive development: Children's knowledge about the mind. *Annual review of psychology*, 50(1), 21-45.
- Siegler, R. S. (2016). *Emerging minds: The process of change in children's thinking*. Oxford University Press.
- Baddeley, A. D., & Hitch, G. (1974). Working memory. *Psychology of Learning and Motivation*, 8, 47-89.
- Cowan, N. (1999). An embedded-processes model of working memory. *Models of working memory: Mechanisms of active maintenance and executive control*, 62-101.
- Baddeley, A. D. (2000). The episodic buffer: a new component of working memory? *Trends in cognitive sciences*, 4(11), 417-423.
- Unsworth, N., & Engle, R. W. (2007). The nature of individual differences in working memory capacity: Active maintenance in primary memory and controlled search from secondary memory. *Psychological review*, 114(1), 104-132.
- Creemers E. (2019). FAUSA adopts policy on the performance indicators. FAUSA News ^.
- Chabot, Lise, *Engaging First Nations Parents in Education: An Examination of Best Practices. A Manifesto for Education in Ontario*, Chiefs of Ontario, 2017.
- Centers for Disease Control and Prevention Division of Adolescent and School Health (2019). Student health and academic achievement. http://www.cdc/HealthyYouth/health_and_academics/index.htm. Retrieved on February 19, 2009.
- Cerini, B, Murray, I and Reiss, M (2018) Student review of the science curriculum: major findings, NESTA, London, <http://www.planet-science.com/sciteach/review/Findings.pdf>

- Cuttance P. (2019). Performance indicators for schooling: A report for Scottish Education.
- Cook, J. (2018). The Importance of Learning ScienceHowEducationK-12. The Importance of Learning Science more: http://www.ehow.com/about_6169591_importance-learning-science.html#ixzz2rfRYkVMh
- Damon, W. (2018). *The moral child: Nurturing children's natural moral growth*. New York: Free Press.
- David C. (2018). Closing the gender gap: gender gaps fact sheet. American association of university women.
- DeCos, P.L. (1997, December). *Readiness for kindergarten: What does it mean?* Sacramento, CA: California Research Bureau, California State Library. Summary available online: <http://www.library.ca.gov/html/statseg2a.cfm#CRB-97-14>. Full document also available online (requires Adobe Acrobat software): <http://www.library.ca.gov/CRB/97/14/97014.pdf>
- Demarest, E.J., Reisner, E.R., Anderson, L.M., Humphrey, D.C., Farquhar, E., & Stein, S.E. (2018). *Review of research on achieving the nation's readiness goal*. Washington, DC: U.S. Department of Education.
- De Guzman Jr. and Guy I (2018). Teacher's Time Management and Student's Academic Achievement in LPU College of Nursing: Basis for an Enhanced Classroom Management Lyceum of the Philippines University Batangas City, Batangas Philippines
- Douglas K. (2016). Educators play key role in promoting gender equity. Horizon. Midwest desegregation assistance center.
- Dunnell P. & O'Loughlin MJ. (2017). A framework for the development of performance indicators in an education system. Paper presented at the annual conference of the Australia.
- Edwards M. (2019). Social change and transformation of human relationship: McGraw Hill INC.
- Elias, M. J., Zins, J. E., Weissberg, R. P., Frey, K. S., Greenberg, M. T., Haynes, N. M., et al. (2017). *Promoting social and emotional learning: Guidelines for educators*. Alexandria, VA: Association for Supervision and Curriculum Development.
- Estes, C. (2019). *Promoting Students Centered Learning in Experiential Education*. Journal of Experiential Education.

- Foster, A. (2018). *Decision criteria for assessing one-dimensionality: An empirical study*. Multivariate behavioral research.
- Freiberg, H. Jerome, (2018) *School Climate: Measuring, Improving and Sustaining Healthy Learning Environments*. Philadelphia, PA: Falmer Press, 2005.
- Galligher-Hayashi, Diane (2019) *Connecting with Aboriginal Students*. *Teacher Librarian*; June; 31,5, pp. 20-24.
- Gagne, E.D., Yekovich, C. W., and Yekovich, F.R (2018). *The Cognitive Psychology of School Learning*.
- Genesee, F. (2019). *Integrating Language and Content: Lessons from Immersion*. Educational Practice Report.
- Good, B. (2018). *Measurement and Evaluation*. Retrieved February 24, 2010 from <http://www.livesearch.msn>
- Griffiths, R. F. (2019). *Time management in telework and other autonomous work environments*. Unpublished doctoral dissertation, Kansas State University.
- Grigg, L. & Sheehan, P. (2019). *Evaluating research: The role of performance indicators*. The University of Queensland.
- Hargreaves, D. (2019). *Education Epidemic – Transforming secondary schools through innovation networks*. London: Demos.
- Hawkins, A. (2018). *Gender and technological imagination. Presented at the American Educational Research Association*, Boston, MA. 2008.
- Herbilla L (2018). *Study habits and time management*. *Katigaman Journal*. Dep.Ed.
- Hilburion C (2019). *Extent of implementation of child-friendly school system: Basis for school performance indicators*. Unpublished material thesis. Rizal Memorial Colleges.
- Oberauer, K. (2019). *Working memory and attention—a conceptual analysis and review*. *Journal of cognition*, 2(1), 1-47.
- Huang, X. & Zhan, Z. (2018). *The compiling of adolescence time management disposition inventory*. *Acta Psychological Sinic*, 33(4), 338-343.

- Brackett, M. A., & Rivers, S. E. (2014). Transforming students' lives with social and emotional learning. *Phi Delta Kappan*, 96(2), 8-13.
- Iyoshi, R. (2019). *Cognitive Tools and Student-centered Learning: Rethinking Tools, Functions and Applications*. Educational Media International.
- Fredrickson, B. L. (2001). The role of positive emotions in positive psychology: The broaden-and-build theory of positive emotions. *American psychologist*, 56(3), 218-226.
- Masten, A. S., & Reed, M. G. (2002). Resilience in development. *Handbook of positive psychology*, 74-88.
- Kessler, R. C., Barker, P. R., Colpe, L. J., Epstein, J. F., Gfroerer, J. C., Hiripi, E., ... & Zaslavsky, A. M. (2003). Screening for serious mental illness in the general population. *Archives of general psychiatry*, 60(2), 184-189.
- Kristjansson, E., Robinson, V., Petticrew, M., MacDonald, B., Krasevec, J., Janzen, L., Greenhalgh, T., Wells, G., MacGowan, J., Farmer, A., Shea, B. J., Mayhew, A., and Tugwell, P., (2007). "School Feeding for Improving the Physical and Psychosocial Health of Disadvantaged Elementary School Children." *Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews*.
- Gough, P. B., & Tunmer, W. E. (1986). Decoding, reading, and reading disability. *Remedial and Special Education*, 7(1), 6-10.
- Levin, S. (2019). *A Comparison of Assessment Practices and Their Effects on Learning Motivation in a Student-centered Learning Environment*. *Journal of Educational Multimedia and Hypermedia*.
- Macintosh, F. (2017). *Teachers' Beliefs about Issues in the implementation of a Student-Centered Learning Environment*. *Educational Technology, Research and Development*.
- Malone, K. & Tranter, P. (2018) "Children Environmental learning and the Use, design and Management of school grounds." *Children, Youth and Environments* 13(2), 2003.
- Mapula (2019) challenges of k-12 program and managements skills of public elementary school principals in Davao city. Unpublished Masteral Thesis
- Martimore, S. (2019). *The Difference Made by Schools: School Effectiveness and School Improvement Studies*. *LARTV Seminar Series*. No. 1
- Perfetti, C. A. (1985). *Reading ability*. Oxford University Press. The author discusses the cognitive processes involved in reading comprehension, including attention,

memory, and language processing. Perfetti also discusses the role of prior knowledge and context in comprehension.

- Kintsch, W. (1988). The role of knowledge in discourse comprehension: A construction-integration model. *Psychological review*, 95(2), 163-182..
- Mendes, K. (2018). *Educational reform in Uganda reflections on policy, partnership, strategy and implementation*, UK department for International Development, London. The Efficiency of Public Education in Uganda, World Bank, Washington, D.C., 208.
- Nation, K., & Snowling, M. J. (2004). Beyond phonological skills: Broader language skills contribute to the development of reading. *Journal of Research in Reading*, 27(4), 342-356.
- Van den Broek, P. (2010). Comprehension during reading: A network of goals, inferences, and strategic processes. In *The Psychology of Reading* (pp. 209-226). Routledge.
- Hattie, J. (2009). *Visible Learning: A synthesis of over 800 meta-analyses relating to achievement*. Routledge.
- Marzano, R. J. (2007). *The Art and Science of Teaching: A Comprehensive Framework for Effective Instruction*. ASCD.
- Darling-Hammond, L., Hyler, M. E., & Gardner, M. (2017). *Effective teacher professional development*. Learning Policy Institute.
- Murphy, N. (2018). *Higher education research policy*. Commonwealth government, Canberra.
- Murray, D. (2019). *World learning, 'child-friendly schools baseline report', child friendly basic education and learning programme*, UNICEF New York, USA.
- Wiggins, G., & McTighe, J. (2005). *Understanding by Design*. ASCD.
- Gottman, J. M., & Levenson, R. W. (2000). The timing of divorce: Predicting when a couple will divorce over a 14-year period. *Journal of Marriage and Family*, 62(4), 737-745.
- Osborne, J, Duschl, R. and Fairbrother, B (2019) *Breaking the Mould? Teaching Science for Public Understanding*, School of Education, King's College London.